

FEATURES OF PSYCHOLOGICAL PREPARATION IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING SWIMMING TO STUDENTS

Menglikulov Khayrulla Alikulovich

Senior Lecturer, Faculty of Sports Activities and Management
Termez State University

Annotation: The article discusses the problem of fear of water among students learning to swim. Timely identification of this feature at the initial stage of teaching students to swim is important for achieving the final result. A method for eliminating this problem in physical education classes during training at a university as part of a swimming course is presented, aimed at overcoming the fear of water and realizing the main goal, namely to teach every student to swim.

Keywords: students, learning, swimming, deep pool, fear, water.

Introduction. Full development of personality and self-realization in life requires not only intellectual and creative abilities, acquired professional knowledge and practical experience, but also a sufficient level of psychophysical state, in particular, physical health, mental and physical performance, psycho-emotional stability [3, 4]. Physical exercises contribute to the formation of a harmoniously developed personality and psychophysical preparation of students.

The use of popular types of physical culture and health activities, namely swimming, allows not only to ensure a sufficient level of physical activity, but also has a positive effect on the psychophysical state of students [1, 2, 5].

An analysis of current research allows us to note that the problem of fear of water remains important and requires further study, research into the nature of the occurrence of this type of fear and improvement of methods for overcoming it [7, 9, 10].

Swimming is the most harmonious and aesthetic physical activity [6, 8, 11]. The process of swimming has a diverse effect on the body, being a powerful means of increasing the fitness of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, stimulating the activity of the gastrointestinal tract and metabolism. Physical activity takes place under conditions that relieve gravitational forces and free the spine from axial load, thereby promoting correction of the musculoskeletal system [3, 7, 13]. At the same time, unsupported support and advancement of the body in water require significant muscular effort to overcome the resistance of the aquatic environment, which develops the muscular system well [12].

Swimming is a type of physical exercise that does not have any side effects: by doing swimming it is impossible to get injured and at the same time improve the entire body [14, 15]. The present requires a higher educational institution not only to prepare a highly qualified specialist in its field, but also to contribute to the harmonious development of students' personalities. Including their physical condition, a sufficient level of health and satisfaction of the emotional needs of both a participant in sporting events, a spectator and a fan. Higher school, as a transitional boundary between school and independent life, is entrusted with great responsibility for the formation of knowledge regarding one's own level of physical fitness, health monitoring and health-saving technologies, respectively [16, 19, 20].

Most university physical education programs include swimming lessons as a means of strengthening and improving the health of the body [3, 17]. Considerable attention is paid to differentiation according to the level of swimming readiness of students during swimming exercises. It is mandatory to teach basic swimming skills to all students who do not have medical contraindications. For students who know how to swim, training in sports swimming methods is provided and further improvement of the classical crawl technique, backstroke technique, turning technique, and starting jump. Classes with students who, at the beginning of their studies at the university, already have a certain technical level of swimming training,

are expected to develop general physical qualities, fitness, and participate in competitions of various levels.

Experience of working with students of Termez State University in the process of physical education allows us to notice that there is a fairly large percentage of students who cannot swim. The issue of psychological readiness, an integral part of which is the absence of fear of water during initial swimming training, is mentioned only in some works [2, 21].

Consequently, it can be noted that methods and techniques for overcoming fear of water when teaching swimming to students in a university setting have not been sufficiently developed. According to the results of a survey conducted at the beginning of the academic year, a significant part of students feel insecure in the aquatic environment. About 40% note that they cannot swim at all, 10% admit that they can swim no more than 5-10 meters. When surveying students, several reasons for their inability to swim were identified:

- 1) the absence of swimming pools or reservoirs near the place of residence;
- 2) not interested in acquiring this skill;
- 3) fear of water.

Thus, it is clear that two directions can be considered in teaching swimming to students; in the future, they will require several different ways to solve practical problems. Swimming training for students who have not reported fear of water can be carried out using standard methodology at any depth of the pool. The experience of working with such students confirms the sustainable consolidation of swimming skills acquired during studies in a shallow pool and their positive implementation in swimming, regardless of depth.

Students who noted a fear of water in the questionnaire can be divided into 3 groups:

- 1) witnessed an accident on the water;
- 2) were personally exposed to the danger of drowning;
- 3) fear of unpleasant sensations from water getting into the eyes and respiratory tract.

The success of teaching swimming to these people depends on their awareness of the reasons for their fear of water. Understanding that their accident on the water occurred due to panic and fear as a result of loss of control over the situation and threat to life is very important. The lack of experience in overcoming such situations and the algorithm in case of their occurrence leads to a negative association of being in the water and perpetuating the feeling of fear of a threat to life.

“Fear is an emotion that arises in situations of threat to the biological or social existence of an individual and is directed towards a source of real or imaginary danger” [5]. The following types of fears are distinguished:

- 1) mental (“mental”): doubt, anxiety;
- 2) emotional (“sensual”): excitement, horror, fear/excitement for a loved one, fear in relationships, insecure mood;
- 3) physical (“instinctive/natural”): numbness, numbness, “coldness,” freezing, bodily fear, inaction. The feeling of horror is a protective reaction of the body, a signal of threat. In this case, coordination of movements sharply deteriorates, control is lost, the activity of the central nervous system is disrupted, and a sharp inhibition of all mental and motor reactions may occur [1, 3].

The physical symptoms that hydrophobia can cause may vary in each case. However, a group of manifestations that may occur are described. Specifically, a person with hydrophobia may have the following physical symptoms when in contact with water: increased heart rate and breathing, hyperventilation or feeling of suffocation, generalized muscle tension, excessive sweating throughout the body or cold sweats, stomach cramps or headaches, feeling unreality or depersonalization, dilated pupils, dizziness, nausea and vomiting.

Uncertainty is distinguished as a form of horror. Uncertainty arises from doubt. Doubts give rise to constant self-control. Every time a person doubts something, he turns his attention to the object of his doubt and receives clear confirmation that there is no need to doubt. Then this experience is consolidated in him, he is convinced that he is doing everything correctly, that is, everything is good.

Doubts are needed to once again check the correctness of your choice of actions. To overcome doubts, every even minor success in learning must be noted, the entire group and individual students must receive the approval and support of the teacher. Thus, it is clear that working with students at the initial stage of learning to swim requires a very careful individual approach. Many years of experience working with students who have a fear of water have shown that in order to achieve a sustainable effect in overcoming the fear of water, it is advisable to conduct training in a deep pool with the obligatory use of aids, namely arm guards.

To achieve sustainable effective results in swimming training in the future, it is necessary to:

1. Determine the level of psychological readiness for learning to swim (I want to learn, I'm not very interested just for the test, I feel the fear of the unknown, I feel the fear of water, I'm terribly afraid of water).
2. Identify stress factors that affect readiness to learn to swim (doubt about one's capabilities and positive results, perceived discomfort from getting water on the face, eyes, nose, loss of one's own control in an unknown situation, dependence on others).

After the survey or questionnaire, distribute students into groups of 5-6 people. Experience shows that it is not effective to group people with a fear of water into one group. Each group must include students who do not have emotional problems from contact with water and who are motivated to learn swimming. In this way, a positive psychological state is created in a group of beginning students, the belief that fear of water can be overcome and everyone can learn to swim, since this is a vital skill that everyone should have and for this you do not need to have any special abilities.

Of particular importance for further successful training is the format of the first lesson at the initial stage of learning to swim, aimed at overcoming hydrophobia in beginning students. At the first lesson in the water, a preparatory conversation is held aimed at explaining the rules of behavior in the pool, examining the pool itself,

walking around the perimeter, finding out the depth in different places of the pool and directly in the place where the training will take place, comparing with and the growth of students, the location of life-saving equipment, meeting the pool instructors.

That is, creating psychological comfort, understanding of safety during training, friendly and attentive attitude of others. It is also important to convince students of the teacher's personal interest in the safety of students' lives and the desire to minimize their discomfort during classes. In the form of a dialogue, discuss possible prerequisites for the occurrence of unforeseen situations (what do you think is the most convenient way to enter the water, how is it more convenient to hold on to the ladder while entering the water). offer to enter and exit the water. Some students may be asked to do this several times. This technique neutralizes the novelty of sensations and emotions regarding changes in the environment. Makes the process of entering the water normal and safe.

However, in cases where a student cannot overcome his fear of water, it is important not to insist. It is necessary to give him the opportunity to sit on a bench and watch others swim. In special cases, a student may not even go into the water during the first lesson. At the same time, it is necessary that the teacher himself is calm and demonstrates confidence in the student's safety and the prospects for further education.

Conclusions. Fear of water is one of the most common types of human fears, which is a serious obstacle to mastering swimming skills. Determining psychological readiness for learning to swim, the sequence of actions during training contributes to the direction of the process and reduces the training time for students suffering from fear of water and gives a lasting effect.

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